

DIGITAL AUDIO - PSYCHOACOUSTICAL LOCALIZATION OF SOUNDS WITHIN THE 3-DIMENSIONAL SOUNDSTAGE

E. J. Garba

Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Federal University of Technology P.M.B. 2076
Yola, Adamawa State.

E-mail: etemigarba@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

As objects vibrate, they cause changes in the air pressure, which our ears perceive as sounds that could be translated by our brains as speech, music or noise (Garba 2007b). The four basic characteristics of sound include frequency, amplitude, harmonics and direction from which a sound is coming. The frequency describes the rate at which the air vibrates per second, measured in hertz (Hz). Amplitude is a measure of the loudness of the sound, while harmonics are the exact integer (or whole number) multiples of the fundamental frequency that are responsible for sonic distinction known as timbre ((Garba 2007b), (Atkinson 2006)). The aforementioned premise establishes the localization of sound within a given 3-dimensional space known as soundstage. This paper, therefore, addresses some practicable solutions with regard to the theories, laws, principles and systems of psychoacoustical localization of sounds during recording, mixing and mastering in digital audio production.

KEYWORDS: air pressure, frequency, amplitude, harmonics, psychoacoustical localization

INTRODUCTION

Psychoacoustics, or the study of human perception of sound, provides an explanation of how the human ear-brain system interprets sound and decodes information from a pair of receivers (ears) into a complete 3-dimensional auditory 'image' (Alton 1994). Localization cues are critical to hearing perception since they provide significant information as to where objects are in space (Turner 2007).

In addition to the room effect, sound pressures at ear canals also change as a function of sound source location relative to a listener. When a sound signal travels through space and reaches a listener's ears, it changes due to complex wave acoustics near the listener's torso, head and pinna (auricle). The free-field transfer functions from a sound source to the ear canal are called head-related transfer functions (HRTF) (Pulkki 2001).

In all, the soundstage is perceived as a three-dimensional space (Garba 2007c):

The height (the y-axis) – covers the TOP and the BOTTOM end of the entire human hearing frequency range (20Hz – 20kHz). This is where equalization is applied.

The length (the x-axis) – makes up the LEFT and the RIGHT channels of stereophonic sounds. This is where panning and stereo image enhancement are applied.

The width (the z-axis) – constitutes the BACK and FRONT space of the soundstage. This is where effects are applied.

Monophonic vs. Stereophonic Sounds

Mono or monophonic describes a system where all the audio signals are mixed together and routed through a single audio channel. The key is that the signal contains no level and arrival time/phase information that would replicate or simulate directional cues (Wiki Recording 2006). While monophonic recording captures the three sound characteristics, it cannot convey direction.

Stereophonic sound is able to provide all four characteristics of a sound, mimicking the way the human ear works (Atkinson 2006). It is comprised of two separate audio channels, left and right. Stereo is meant to provide a more natural and pleasing sound by allowing the sound to be perceived as coming from a sound field between speakers rather than just the speaker itself (Wiki Recording 2006).

True stereophonic sound systems have two independent audio signal channels and the signals that are reproduced have a specific level and phase relationship to each other so that when played back through a suitable reproduction system, there will be an apparent image of the original sound source. Stereo would be a requirement if there is a need to replicate the aural perspective and localization of sounds on a stage or platform (Wiki Recording 2006).

Systems that play back stereophonic sound use separate speakers for the different recorded signals. When the speakers are in the proper position relative to the listener, the sound from the speakers has the directional quality of the original sound (Atkinson 2006).

The Haas Effect

The psychoacoustic phenomenon referred to as Precedence Effect or Haas Effect states that “the earliest of any closely spaced group of similar sounds provides the strongest directional clues”. That is, when auditioning with loudspeakers, we do not only listen to direct sounds, but their reflections (also known as reverberation) from the various surfaces in the soundstage. Also, each ear does not only hear from its direct source (as in the case of headphones); this

means sounds coming from the left (right) speaker also reaches the right (left) ear (with minor delay, though) (Garba 2007c).

The precedence effect is an assisting mechanism of spatial hearing. It is a suppression of early delayed versions of the direct sound in source direction perception. This helps in reverberant rooms to localize sound sources. In a reverberant room when the reflections reach the listener, they are summed up to the direct sound, which changes the binaural cues prominently (Pulkki 2001). This phenomenon is responsible for the major technical difference between auditioning with headphones and loudspeakers.

The Panning Laws

Panning refers to placing the audio in the stereo field. A pan control allows the placement of the signal hard left, hard right, or anywhere in between. When working with stereo, sounds are evenly or unevenly spread between two output signals, using a device called a panoramic potentiometer, or “panpot.” If the instrument is equally loud in both signals, it appears to be in the center. If it is present in only one signal, it appears to be all the way to the left or right (Atkinson 2006).

Fig. 2 Typical Panning System in Contemporary Music

The aim of a good panning law is to take monophonic sounds, and to give each one amplitude gains, one for each loudspeaker, dependent on the intended illusory directional localization of that sound, such that the resulting reproduced sound provides a convincing and sharp phantom illusory image. Such a good panning law should provide a smoothly continuous range of image directions for any direction between those of the two outermost loudspeakers (West 1998). In a stereophonic recording, separate loudspeakers play back the signal from the original microphone, called the channel (Eargler 1996). Listeners need to be equally distant from each speaker to get the best of stereo sound. If the listener is closer to one of the speakers, then the stereo sound image will be pulled to one side, due to the Haas effect or the precedence effect (Atkinson 2006).

Panning laws determine how the level of the signal is altered as it is panned. These laws were originally developed to counteract the tendency of sounds in the middle of the stereo field to

be louder than sounds that were panned hard left or right (Anderton 2006). Panning law uses a logarithm to lower the level of the signal as it gets closer to center. This keeps the perceived volume of the signal the same across the stereo field (Wiki Recording 2006).

Technically, panning is achieved by a linear gain increase in one channel and a linear gain decrease in the other. The resultant effect is that the stereo position of the sound is pushed to the side of the louder channel. But it has been discovered that the sum of the two channels at the center position sounds louder than if the signal was panned either full left or full right (Robjohns 2005). In order to compensate for this, most modern panning laws use a logarithmic gain change response which permits the RMS (sound level) at the center to be dropped by -6dB, 4.5dB, -3dB or 0dB (Garba 2007c).

Panning laws vary between electronic, hardware and software products, depending on whether they are designed to maintain constant voltage, constant power, or a compromise between the two. The compromised version is probably the most prevalent these days, with pan pots designed to provide something like a 4.5dB attenuation when at the centre. Constant power gives 3dB of centre attenuation, while constant voltage gives 6dB attenuation (Wiki Recording 2006).

If identical signals are panned fully left and right, there will be full-level signals in each output channel. However, if the signal is panned to the centre, the left and right outputs will be attenuated by 4.5dB (in the case of the common 'compromise' panning law). But because both input channels are panned to the centre, each output channel is receiving two lots of signal, each 4.5dB lower than the level of a single channel panned fully left or right. Since the two signals are identical, they will sum together and the level will rise by 6dB. Therefore, the difference between 6dB and -4.5dB is calculated and each output channel is now carrying a summed mix of +1.5dB. Hence, each output channel is now carrying a signal that is 1.5dB higher than it was when the channels were individually panned left and right (Wiki Recording 2006).

For instance, if a stereo system employed the constant power law, with 3dB central attenuation, the two channels panned centrally would produce an output of +3dB in each channel, while a system with the constant voltage law would produce an output that is exactly the same level as the fully panned channels (in terms of signal voltage, at least). The constant power panning law is used where a panned signal is required to remain at more or less the same perceived volume regardless of where it is panned. (Wiki Recording 2006).

Setting the value to 0dB eliminates constant-power panning, which results to the old-fashioned "center-channel-louder" effect. However, the true and tested "drop the center by -3dB" classic equal power setting has become widely accepted. Note that some applications/sequencers allow the user to choose panning laws; most however, do not make these options transparent (Garba 2007c).

Panning System of Stereo Field

In contemporary music, each instrument that makes up the rhythm track has its position in space. This gives the track an instrumental distinction, with a fuller and a clearer soundstage. Technically, this spatial arrangement of instruments helps in preventing frequency masking and elimination of phase cancellation. Rhythm track instruments are panned from either 0% (center) to 100% left or right. Typically, the bass guitar, the kick (bass drum) and the snare are centered. Hi-hats are panned slightly to the right, while the rides are panned slightly to the left. The toms, in descending order of pitch, cover half-left and half-right. Percussions are panned

100% left or right ((Garba 2003), (Garba 2007c)).

Even though one is free to devise his own panning system, remember that low-end instruments, such as the bass, the kick, the snare should remain centered to give a stable mix and to avoid their unbalanced perception on either the left or the right channels of the speakers (this is very evident while listening to music thru head/earphones). Take a mental note of this because low frequencies contain most of the energy within the mix; thus, it is best to share the load of reproducing them across both stereo channels (left/right) ((Garba 2003),(Garba 2007c)).

Multiband Stereo Delay

Naturally, both ears hear both direct and reflected sounds with slight time variations due to the location of the source of the sound. For instance, if the source is closer to the right ear, then the left ear would be receiving direct sounds with slight delays in milliseconds. This natural phenomenon can be recreated to give the mix an extra depth and width. This is achievable using the stereo delay line. Use 20 – 30ms delay; and then pan the wet signals to either full-left/full-right. The resultant effect is that the sound will appear to come from the undelayed side (even if the signal levels are equal on both channels). This is due to a psychoacoustic phenomenon referred to as Precedence Effect or Haas Effect (Garba 2007c).

During digital audio mastering, the Multiband Stereo delay tool could be used to change the stereo position of the bands without panning. Multiband Stereo delay is not an echo effect! It is applied to a mix when mastering to add some natural characteristics (such as Haas Effect) to the sound. This tool helps to generate this pseudo-Haas Effect (Garba 2007a).

Stereo Widening

Stereo widening processing algorithm is used to provide a system and method for giving a listener an impression that a stereo audio signal having left and right channels is emanating from a virtual source, spaced away from left and right stereo loudspeakers. This algorithm, which works particularly well when the loudspeakers are spaced apart by a distance that is less than optimal without noticeably affecting the sound quality of the stereo audio signal when played on the loudspeakers (Nokia Corporation 2005).

Effects

Effects are primarily designed to modify sounds within the 3-D soundstage. The resulting sound, however, is the mixture of the original sound (known as the dry signal) and the modified sound (known as the wet signal). In most effect devices (such as reverb, delay, chorus), one is free to set the ratio between the dry and wet signal levels as so desired (Garba 2007c).

Effects modify the dynamics, the phase and the stereo image of the sounds. That is why wet (effected) signals, to a certain degree, lose their presence and definition in the mix. On the other hand, dry/unprocessed audio signals usually sound upfront (Garba 2007c).

Reverberation (simply known as reverb) is an effect that simulates different types of acoustic spaces. It works by recreating a seemingly infinite number of waves bouncing around a reverberant space of the 3-D soundstage (Garba 2007b). Reverb creates the illusion of space,

but in doing so, it also smears the stereo localization of the original sound source (White 1999).

Localization of sounds within the soundstage is achievable by manipulating the parameters that control the three basic components of sound in a given reverberant space. These components include the Direct Sound, Early Reflections and the Reverb (late reflections) (Garba 2007c).

Direct Sound – This is the original sound straight from the source to the listener without any delay or reflections from various surfaces of the room.

Early Reflections – They consists of the first few reflected sounds. They arrive later than the direct sound in a couple of milliseconds. They determine the size of the 3-D soundstage.

Reverb (late reflections) – This is a group of continuously reflected sounds after the early reflections. The time taken for the reverberation to die or fade away is called the Decay time. It depends on the number of surfaces (things, people, etc) in a space.

A pseudo-stereo effect could be created by using a fairly gentle mono chorus effect on one of the channels of the stereo sounds. The resultant chorus effect creates stereo movement between the speakers; and at the same time producing a spacious and rich sound within the sound stage (Garba 2007c).

Equalization

Primarily, equalization has two main functions during mixing. First, it is used to adjust the tone of each sound. Second, it creates level balances between the various bands (low, mid and high) that make up the sound. This may mean either attenuating or boosting some portions of the sounds (Garba 2007c). Note however, that one of the major challenges of achieving equalization lies in the Fletcher-Munson Effect. This phenomenon asserts, “*Humans do not hear the low frequencies (bass) and the extreme high frequencies (treble) as well at low volumes*”. This means therefore, that human ears are noticeably more sensitive to mid-range sounds than to both low and high frequencies; but we don't actually notice this because the brain compensates for it.

Therefore, use hi-shelve equalization settings to make some sounds have less presence within the soundstage. This is where the bell curve is most suitable when certain sounds are required to have more presence than others.

CONCLUSION

A mix with realistic spacious soundstage is only obtainable when sounds are heard from different parts of the 3D space. This means that some sounds would have to sound more upfront or louder than others; while various sounds will have to emerge from different directions of the speakers (Garba 2007c). Therefore, in digital audio production, the use of artificial digital effects (reverb, delay, chorus, etc), panning, stereo image widening and multiband stereo delay on stereophonic sounds help in achieving more stereo depth and width. This also guarantees the reproduction and generation of sounds with desired psycho-acoustical localizations within the 3-D soundstage.

REFERENCES

- Alton, Everest F. (1994): *The Master Handbook of Acoustics*, 3rd Edition, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Anderton, Craig (2006): *Panning Laws Revealed*, Harmony Central, http://www.harmony-central.com/articles/tips/panning_laws/ (accessed December 10, 2007).
- Atkinson, John (2006): *Stereophonic Sound*, Microsoft® Student 2007 [DVD], Microsoft Corporation Redmond, WA, USA.
- Eargle, John M. (1996): *Handbook of Recording Engineering*, 3rd Edition, Chapman & Hall, New York.
- Garba, E. J. (2003): *Computer Music – Rhythm Programming, Processing and Mastering*, Trafford Publishing, Canada.
- Garba, E. J. (2007a): *Digital Audio Mastering with Reason*, Audiophilia Records, Nigeria.
- Garba, E. J. (2007b): *Digital Audio Production & Music Technology (An introductory guide)*, Audiophilia Records, Nigeria.
- Garba, E. J. (2007c): *Music Arranging & Mixing with Reason*, Audiophilia Records, Nigeria.
- Nokia Corporation (2005): *Transparent stereo widening algorithm for loudspeakers*, <http://www.freepatentsonline.com/6928168.html> (accessed December 10, 2007).
- Pulkki, Ville (2001): *Spatial Sound Generation and Perception by Amplitude Panning Techniques*, Helsinki University of Technology Laboratory of Acoustics and Audio Signal Processing, Finland.
- Robjohns, Hugh (2005): *Why is the signal louder when it is panned to the centre?*, Sound On Sound Ltd, UK. www.soundonsound.com/sos/nov05/articles/qa1106_6.htm (accessed December 10, 2007).
- Turner, Andrew (2007): *The Basics of Psychoacoustics with Respect to Localization*, Illumin, USA.
- West, Jim (1998): *IID-based Panning Methods “Rationale for IID-based Panning”*, University of Miami, USA.
- White, Paul (1999): *20 Tips on Using Effects in the Mix*, Sound On Sound, Media House, Trafalgar Way, Bar Hill, Cambridge CB3 8SQ, UK.
- Wiki Recording (2006): *Panning*, GNU Free Documentation, <http://www.wikirecording.org/Panning> (accessed December 10, 2007).

Received for Publication: 21/02/2008

Accepted for Publication: 13/04/2008